

SUN COLLECTORS STRUCTURE VA WORK TRENDS

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The first model of a solar collector was created in the late 18th century by the Swiss scientist Goratzion Sossiur, and was a device consisting of a glass and wooden box with a layer of heating inside. At that time, the scientist realized that it was "small, cheap and simple." Such devices began to be used in practice in the late 19th century to heat hot water in Southern California. A simple solar collector in the form of a water tank covered with black paint, covered with a closed glass facing the sun, began to be produced. In such collectors the water was not hot in the evening, it was necessary to wait the next day for it to heat up. In 1909, William Bailey created the modern flat collector in California. In this case, the water-filled tank was separate from the device, and the heat going to it was through the heat exchange circuit (Figure 1.1.1).

1.1.1 - picture. Schematic view of a simple solar collector.

By the end of the 1940s, the solar collector manufacturing industry had reached its peak in the southern states of California and Florida. Shortly afterwards, the use of electricity and gas, the cost of generating hot water fell, and the production of solar collectors ceased.

The second phase of production of solar collectors dates back to the 1970s. As the global oil crisis erupted and energy prices soared, many countries around the world, including the United States, Japan, Australia, and

the Mediterranean, began to use solar panels. Production in quantities of 'p has been set up.

In the 1950s, severe energy shortages in Israel reached such a level that the government passed a law in the evening to suspend hot water supply. Since then, the country has been developing the production of solar devices for hot water generation. By 1967, 20% of the country's population used a solar collector. During the energy crisis of the 1970s, parliament passed a law requiring a solar heating system to be available for every newly built home. Today, solar collectors provide 85% of the energy consumed in households in this country. The amount of energy produced in them is 3% of the country's energy supply. This means that 2 million people a year in the country. barrels of oil have been saved.

By the year 2000, rising energy prices ushered in a new phase in the use and production of solar collectors. By the beginning of 2010, 150GW of solar collectors had been installed on the entire planet, excluding solar pools and air collectors. Solar collectors with a capacity of more than 30 GW are installed every year, and today the total capacity of solar collectors in the world produces more than 250 GW of heat energy, and this figure continues to grow . In particular, in China in 2012, the total area of solar collectors was 145 million cubic meters, and the total amount of thermal energy they provided exceeded 100 GWh. In comparison, all nuclear power plants in Russia have four times the capacity of the combined power plant. Interestingly, 15 years ago, there were almost no solar collectors in China. Initially, the development of production in this area was carried out, but today the government has allowed to expand the creation of collectors that are useful for the population. Because the use of a solar collector is very cost-effective, during its service life the solar collector produces such an amount of energy that it is covered by several times the cost of building the device.

To date, solar collectors have become the most efficient device in the use of solar energy. If photovoltaic panels use 14-18% of the incident solar energy, this efficiency in the solar collector will reach 70-80% .

Depending on the temperature, we will consider solar collectors in the following types:

1. *Low temperature collectors* - such collectors produce a temperature not exceeding 50°C. These are used in cases where high temperatures are not required, such as heating water in pools (Figure 1.1.2).

2. *Medium temperature collectors* - this can heat water to 50 - 80°C. Most often, such a collector is a flat glass plate, which is a device consisting of a liquid as a heat carrier.

3. *High-temperature collectors* often have the appearance of a parabola, which often operates in relatively large systems, where it collects electricity and distributes it throughout the city electricity.

Figure 1.1.2–. Scheme of heating the pool using a solar collector.

One of the simplest forms of solar collectors to date is air collectors. These are also called thermosyphon collectors. The reason for this is that the generator simultaneously absorbs heat and retains the heated water at its expense, such collectors often heat the water to raise the initial temperature of gas and electrical appliances, which are standard devices. Using this method, you can save power. Let's look at the advantages of this collector: first, it saves electricity. Second, it is used in solar water heating systems, which are considered relatively cheap enough. Third, the maintenance of the device is much simpler, such collectors are called "Integrated Collector and storage" or simply prefabricated collectors. It often has one or more tanks filled with water. These tanks are placed inside a heat-protected box and covered with a glass lid, sometimes with a reflector placed inside the box to collect the falling sunlight. The operation of this device is quite simple. Solar energy passing through the glass heats the water. A device serviced in this way is cheaper, but it is necessary to protect the water from freezing in cold weather (Figure 1.1.3) .

1.1.2 - picture. Solar air collector.

The temperature of the air in the collector differs from the ambient temperature by $3-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The reason for such a low FIC is the presence of heat loss through convection and radiation. When the absorbing surface is coated with any transparent substance that has a low conductivity relative to infrared radiation, it reduces the rate of heat loss. The reason is that the air flow collects under the absorbing surface or between the absorbing surface and this transparent coating. A transparent coating made of glass or plastic does not have the ability to significantly reduce the level of heat radiation emitted from the absorbing surface. However, it reduces convective heat loss, which allows the temperature to be raised to $20 - 50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, the intensity of solar energy falling on the collector and the quality of the air climate also depend on this parameter. A common advantage of these is that there is also a reduction in heat loss with radiation due to a decrease in the absorbing surface temperature. However, it should also be noted that a decrease in the energy absorbed by the absorbent occurs due to the collision of the air stream (Figure 1.1.4).

Figure 1.1.4. General view and scheme of a simple air collector.

A solar device in the form of a flat collector is used for heating water consumption and domestic heating systems. At first glance, this device looks like a simple metal box, but inside it is a black plate that absorbs sunlight well. This box lid must be made of glass or plastic that conducts solar energy well.

The glass part of a flat solar collector is transparent or opaque, often causing the glass to be completely opaque to sunlight, such that the glass only transmits light. In particular, a very low amount of iron is added to the glass, which helps to transmit the bulk of the light falling on the collector. Its operation is as follows: The solar energy falling on the plate, called the heat sink plate, is converted into heat energy on the spot, and the glass acts as a heat shield that serves to increase the collector FIC. Its walls also act as a heat shield, such a design minimizes heat loss (Figure 1.1.5).

The reason why the sunlight absorber plate or absorbent is painted black is to increase the amount of solar energy being absorbed. This is because an absolutely black body absorbs the entire range of the incident radiation regardless of the wavelength.

Figure 1.1.5. Schematic view of a flat solar collector.

The solar energy that falls on the absorbing plate through the glass is sent here to the heat carrier to continue the process of converting it into heat energy. In this case, the heat carrier is air or liquid circulating in the pipes. Unfortunately, the darkened surface also reflects 10% of the Sun's radiation. To limit this condition, an additional special coating is applied to the winning plate. Such a coating lasts longer than a surface painted with ordinary paint and also allows to increase the collector FIC. Examples of such coatings include amorphous semiconductor layers. Which they spray on a plate, the base of which is metal. The absorbing plates are made of metal that conducts heat well, the high thermal conductivity of the metal leads to a reduction in heat loss during the transfer of recycled energy to the heat carrier. Such metals include aluminum and copper. The difference between these two metals is that copper has better thermal conductivity and corrosion resistance than aluminum plate (Figure 1.1.6).

Figure 1.1.6. General view and scheme of flat solar collector.

A - Solar energy absorbing part; B - The part that heats the water and converts it into electricity; 1 - Heat-protected part; 2 - Glass layer; 3 - Photoelectric panel; 4- Evaporation area of the substance in the heat pipes; 5 - Electric heating parts; 6 - Filters; 7 - Heat absorbing layer; 8 - Heat exchange section; 9 - Area of condensation of liquid in heat pipes. It is known that not using glass of air collectors significantly reduces economic costs. In this case, the collector is made of perforated metal. Whichever is black, such a material allows to improve the quality of heat exchange. The working

process of this process is that the metal heats up fast enough. The connected fan draws hot air through a hole in the metal floor. Collectors of this type are used in settlements, most often their size is 2.4 - 0.8 m. The velocity of the heated air is 0.002 m / s. Even on a sunny winter day, the air temperature in the collector varies by up to 28 ° C compared to the outside. So, it is necessary to improve the quality of air flow from outside. In industrial models of such collectors, their FIC reaches up to 70%, and their cost can be reduced by the materials used (Figure 1.1.7).

Figure 1.1.7. Schematic of a mirror air collector.

1- T thin coating; 2 - Y collecting surface; 3- Q return screen; 4- I heat insulation; 5 - Corps.

Parabolaclindrical reflector concentrators located under the absorbing element are used to raise the operating temperature of solar collectors to 120 - 250°C. In order to obtain a higher temperature, this device must have the ability to automatically slide across the Sun.

The main difference between focused solar collectors and the above-mentioned collector is that it uses concentrated solar radiation. Using the mirror surfaces, the returning solar energy is directed to the exact absorbing surface (Figure 1.1.8). The temperature in such a collector is high enough even above the maximum temperature in a flat collector, but it should be borne in mind that the concentrators do not receive anything other than direct solar radiation. This means that they are not available in cloudy climates. This type of collector-concentrators works well in areas closer to the equator.

Figure 1.1.8. Focused Solar Collectors (Concentrators).

For more efficient operation of the concentrator, a special device is used that slides in the direction of sunlight. Depending on the axis of rotation, such collectors are divided into collectors with single-axis and two-axis turning device. While a single-axis rotation device can move from east to west, a two-axis rotation device can also move around the four corners of the globe. This collector-concentrator is used in the production line. Because the cost of this device is high enough and requires constant maintenance, it is not suitable for domestic maintenance.

In places where the planet is relatively high in solar radiation, flat solar collectors were first used. However, in cold, windy and cloudy weather, the efficiency of this type of collector at full capacity is significantly reduced. It also keeps some of the collector's internal parts from excess moisture and some inconvenience from performing well in its function. As a result, the collector service time is reduced. Vacuum solar collectors are used to overcome such shortcomings.

Figure 1.1.9 . Vacuum Solar Collector .

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Flat The sun collectors The sun nurini absorber , transparent __ layer and from the heat protection seeker from the floor consists of which was _ parts structured _ The winner surface heat o ' conductor system with bog liq _ will be . _ SHE IS black rang or efficiency increase for necessary which was _ special mixed article with covered . The transparent surface is usually made of tempered glass or polycarbonate mixed glass with low metal content.

The back of the device is made of a heat-insulating material, such as polysocyanurite. Water distribution pipes are made of polyethylene or copper, and the panel itself is made of airtight material, usually silicone. If we ensure that no excess heat escapes from the flat collector, it can heat water from 190 to 200 ° C. The higher the amount of energy entering the heat carrier in the collector, the higher its efficiency. It can also be enhanced by placing a special optical coating that does not emit light in the red spectrum.

a)

b)

Figure 1.1.10. a) General view of the vacuum solar collector; b) Schematic of a vacuum solar collector; 1 - Connect; 2 - Silicon layer; 3 - EPDM layer; 4 - Vacuum tube made of impact-resistant glass; 5 - Aluminum absorbing surface with high selective layer; 6 - Mirror reflector, 7 - Collector outer shell; 8 - U-shaped tube designed to absorb heat from the absorbing surface.

In the standard solution to increase the efficiency of the collector, copper is used as the absorbing surface, because its thermal conductivity is very high, and sometimes aluminum is also used as the absorbing surface. Although the thermal conductivity is twice as low as that of copper, the power reserve of aluminum metal is high. Hence, this metal has the property of retaining the energy coming in during heat transfer

Even with a limited amount of incoming energy, it is possible to increase the temperature of the heat carrier to 250 - 300°C. This can be done by reducing the heat loss due to the use of multi-layer glass coating, high tightness, or by creating a vacuum collector

The structure of a solar heat pipe is similar to a thermos used in domestic life. Only the outside of the tube is transparent, while the inside is covered with a highly selective coating that traps solar energy, and a vacuum is created between the outer and inner glass tube. The vacuum layer in the exact space allows to store 95% of the stored heat energy, in addition, the heat pipes in vacuum solar collectors also act as heat carriers. When the liquid in the lower part of the tube is heated by sunlight, it heats up into steam. The steam rises to the top of the tube (condenser), i.e. it cools by transferring its heat to the collector. The use of this method gives a high FIC compared to a flat collector, especially in climatic conditions with low temperatures and low levels of radiation.

In domestic service solar collectors, heat carriers such as water, air, oil or antifreeze are circulated through the collector when heated, then transfer their heat energy to the accumulator, providing a backup hot water for the consumer.

In the simplest types of this device, the water circulation occurs naturally due to the temperature differences between the collector and above it the tank-accumulator. In a slightly more complex type it will have its own part filled with water or antifreeze. In this section, a pump is connected to the circulation of the heat carrier, the tank can be installed directly with the collector or inside the building.

a) b)

Figure 1.1.11. a) Schematic diagram of a single-circuit collector ; b) Schematic diagram of a two-loop collector ; 1- Solar collector; 2 - N basis; 3- B ak-accumulator; 4 - B controller; 5 - N control and control device; 6- I heat exchanger.

When solar energy is not enough to raise the water temperature to the desired level, an additional electric heater is placed behind the tank-accumulator. This method allows you to increase the efficiency of the solar system. In particular, the Solar Collector is used more in cases where the FIC decreases as the temperature of the heat carrier increases. There are also types of solar water heaters in the form of accumulators - a separate tank without a battery - heated water stored directly in the solar collector. In this case, the appearance of the device will be close to the appearance of a right-angled tank.

Solar air collectors are devices that operate using solar energy and heat the air. It is often in the form of simple flat collectors and is mainly used for heating buildings and drying agricultural products. In this case, the air passes through the absorbing surface using natural convection or a fan. Because air conducts heat poorly relative to a liquid, it transfers less heat to a heat-absorbing surface than a liquid-based heat carrier. Some solar air heaters have a fan attached to the absorber plates, which increase heat turbulence and improve heat transfer. The disadvantage of this device is that the presence of additional energy consumption for the operation of the fan leads to an increase in the cost of this system. In cold climates, the air is directed along the channel between the plate-absorbing surface and heats the back wall of the collector, resulting in additional heat loss across the glass. However, if the ambient temperature does not exceed 17°C, the air circulating bilaterally from the plate-absorbing surface will work effectively without

excessive heat loss. The main advantages of air collectors are their simplicity and reliability. Used with care, it can last 10 to 20 years. In addition, heat exchange element exchange is not observed because the air does not freeze.

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